

PANICOOCENE

REFRAMING CLIMATE CHANGE-INDUCED MOBILITIES

Contract no. **101105719**

PANICOOCENE

PANICOOCENE. Reframing Climate Change-induced Mobilities

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Version	Date (DD/MM/YYYY)	Created/Amended by	Changes
1	02/05/2024	Elena Giacomelli	Initial version submitted to the EC as deliverable

Scheduled Data Management Plan (DMP) Updates

The DMP is a document that evolves during the lifespan of the project and registers all relevant changes in the life-cycle of all the research datasets. Updated versions of the DMP have already been planned. Moreover, this document will be updated whenever important changes in the data or the data management policy occur.

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Data Management Plan (DMP)

This DMP provides details on all the research data collected and generated within the PANICOCENE project. In particular, it explains the way research data are handled, organized, licensed, and made available to the public, and how they will be preserved after the project is completed.

This DMP reflects the current state of the art of the PANICOCENE project. However, the details and the final number of datasets may vary during the research project. The variations will be recorded in updated versions of this DMP.

1. Data Summary

The project aims to identify and analyze the ways by which news media may lead to stereotyping climate change-induced mobilities (CCIM), thus impacting on perceptions of readerships, general audiences and ultimately policy-making, and to propose a space for collaboration between activists, journalists and academics.

In order to achieve the overall goals of the project, the researcher will collect qualitative data, review existing literature, and analyze pre-existing datasets.

The project will reuse data from the following sources:

- Sakellari, M. (2023). Key Climate Change Communicators' Perceptions of Climate Migration in the UK [Data set]. <https://b2share.eudat.eu/https://doi.org/10.23728/B2SHARE.3CC2C884C84845218472D81609E991D1> (<https://b2share.eudat.eu/records/3cc2c884c84845218472d81609e991d1>)
- Climate migration (CNAP). https://osf.io/s2bnt/?view_only=3bf64fc539bf4b78a04150aa34a7dcc0

Standards file formats (docx./PDF for text, and .dta/XLS/CSV for datasets) will be used to allow end users to convert files to other formats, depending on their preference.

The project will also produce different types of data by using different methodologies:

1. Qualitative data from semi-structured interviews in the different project sites;
2. Qualitative materials generated in the context of workshops and focus groups;
3. Qualitative data from critical discourse analysis of narratives and discourse on CCIM
4. Platform (free access and registration on a voluntary basis): identification data, role, gender, and contact data.

The research team has agreed to convert research data from proprietary formats to well-known and documented open formats to facilitate accessibility and reusability (Tab.1).

Table 1 - Summary of data formats

Type of data	Formats used during data processing	Formats for sharing, reuse and preservation
1- Qualitative data from semi-structured interviews in the different project sites	DOC, Proprietary audio-visual formats, Nvivo	OTD, MP3, MP4

Type of data	Formats used during data processing	Formats for sharing, reuse and preservation
2- Qualitative materials generated in the context of workshops and focus groups	Various proprietary audio-visual formats, Nvivo	OTD, MP3, MP4, JPEG, Georeferenced TIFF, AI, Shapefiles
3- Qualitative data from critical discourse analysis of narratives and discourse on CCIM	Various proprietary formats, Nvivo	OTD, MP3, MP4, JPEG, Georeferenced TIFF, AI, Shapefiles
4- Platform (free access and registration on a voluntary basis): identification data, role, gender, contact data.	Various proprietary formats	HTML; TXT

README files¹ explaining all relevant details regarding data collection, processing methodologies, and quality assurance will be deposited along with the datasets in .odt, .rtf, or .pdf format.

The expected size of the data collected (nor of each of the datasets) through PANICOCENE’s activities is not yet known but is expected to be quite big (between 100GB to 4TB) due to the diversity of sources. Considering the early stage of the project, the effective size may vary with respect to what is declared here. Potential variations will be addressed in further versions of this document.

The data produced within the framework of the PANICOCENE project can be of interest to different potential users. In particular, they may include external researchers (through scientific articles, workshops, and dissemination of datasets). It will also benefit anyone interested in the field of climate change and migration, including populations affected by climate change themselves; journalists; activists and artists; students; NGOs; international organizations (such as IOM, UNHRC) as well as local, national and regional policy-makers (including the European Union) especially through the delivery of narrative recommendations).

2. FAIR Data

Making data “FAIR” means making it Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. This section will describe the strategies that the PANICOCENE project has set in place to achieve this.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To improve the findability of research data produced during the project, the dataset will be deposited in trusted data repositories if and when appropriate. In addition, whenever project results are published, the team members deposit and describe the relative underlying datasets in trusted data repositories in order to guarantee their discoverability, access, and preservation beyond the project end.

¹ A “README” file is a document containing relevant information about dataset authorship, terms of reuse and responsibilities, explaining dataset content and structure, collection procedures and analysis (such as file specifics, methodologies, codebooks of variables, data sources, and further necessary notes). (See Annex II to visualize the suggested README file template).

The chosen repositories (see section 2.2, Table 2) attribute a unique persistent identifier (PID) to the deposited items, specifically a digital object identifier (DOI) provided by the repository of choice. The unique identifiers are then used to cite the datasets within all research publications.

They also support standard descriptive metadata to ensure dataset indexing and discoverability.

In addition, the metadata will also include the following:

- A digital object identifier (DOI) provided by the repository of choice;
- Keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use;
- The publication date and length of embargo period;
- The disclaimer prepared for PANICOCENE publications, which acknowledges EU funding and includes the name of the action (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Global Fellowship), acronym (PANICOCENE) and grant number (101105719);
- License and link to license: Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license;
- A data disclaimer for the re-use of data associated with the CC license

Specific keywords will be associated to each dataset to enhance semantic discoverability: [Mobilities; migration; climate change; Media; Narratives and Discourses].

Research data are organized in datasets named collections of data units with the same focus and scope. In this DMP we set out common rules for dataset naming to improve data visibility, discoverability, citation, and permanent online tracking.

The recommended dataset title structure consists of:

PROJECT ACRONYM. Task title or description. Additional information (if necessary). Version number

Example:

PANICOCENE. Academics interview. v0.1

The version number of the dataset will be added at the end of the title in case of data revisions to help identify the dataset updates especially in repositories that do not track versioning automatically (see Annex I).

This DMP also recommends the following rules for file naming:

- for dataset file(s)

[PROJECT ACRONYM]_TaskNumber_Coverage or other content specifications_Date(YYYYMMDD)_VersionNumber.fileExtention

Example:

PANICOCENE_Academics interview_20240210_v0.1.odt

- for README file(s)

[PROJECT ACRONYM]_TaskNumber_Coverage or other content specifications_Date(YYYYMMDD)_VersionNumber_README.fileExtention

Example:

PANICOCENE_Academics interview_20240210_v0.1_README.txt

2.2 Making data accessible

As a guiding principle, PANICOCENE seeks to make all research data openly available as soon as possible and ensure open access — via the repository — to allow dissemination, validation and re-use of research results.

To this purpose, all possible and legitimate actions and strategies are adopted to allow data sharing including:

- converting the files to standard open formats;
- providing all relevant documentation and explanation for the data and the datasets;
- obtaining copyright permissions from third-party data owners to be allowed to re-use, reproduce and distribute the collected data;
- obtaining the informed consent of stakeholders involved, and anonymizing and aggregating the data from interviews/workshops/focus groups;
- in case of copyright on raw data derived, collected or elaborated from pre-existing databases or other original sources (i.e. papers, journal articles, book chapters, reports, video and audio sources), collected data will be made available if the reproduction and sharing are allowed by expressed permission of the right holders or by applicable copyright exceptions and exemptions. Otherwise, only aggregate data resulting from the analysis will be openly published. When the sources are freely available online in their original repositories, but direct reproduction is not allowed, a detailed account of how the dataset was created from the original data will be provided, together with the specification of open repositories from where the original datasets are available. Raw data consisting in full texts will not be made available without the copyright holders' permission.

Restrictions to access are applied only in the following cases:

- collected data belonging to third parties that have denied permission for sharing on account of confidentiality and proprietary issues;
- personal data of key informants involved in surveys, focus groups, interviews, and case studies must be protected;
- data availability would jeopardize the project's main aim.

See Annex I for details on the accessibility of each dataset. In all cases, metadata will be made openly available and licensed under a “No Rights Reserved” CC0 license or equivalent, as per the Grant Agreement, and will contain information on how to access the data.

The data repositories chosen guarantee long-term preservation and attribute persistent unique identifiers to the archived datasets. They support open licenses and different access levels. Finally, they adopt descriptive metadata standards such as Dublin Core and DataCite Metadata Schema, as required by the OpenAIRE guidelines², and allow cross-linking between publications and the relevant datasets. Please see the table below for more details.

² OpenAIRE, <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

Table 2 – Summary of repositories.
The following table shows the repositories for dataset publication and preservation.

Repository name	Type	URL	PID	OpenAIRE compatibility?
AMSacta	Institutional	https://amsacta.unibo.it/	DOI	Yes
Zenodo	General purpose repository	https://zenodo.org/	DOI	Yes

2.3 Making data interoperable

All datasets will be described using standard descriptive metadata, to ensure metadata interoperability for indexing and discoverability. For each deposited dataset, relevant documentation explaining data collection procedures and analysis is made available along with the data, to guarantee intelligibility, reproducibility and the validation of the project findings.

As mentioned, the team will convert all shareable data from proprietary formats to well-known and documented open formats (see section 1, Table 1). This allows data exchange and re-use between different researchers, institutions, organisations and countries.

If specific software is used during data processing, the deposited documentation will include full explanation and instructions.

2.4 Increasing data re-use

PANICOCENE distributes the shareable data by adopting licenses that allow re-use of the data and of the data sets in their entirety by other scholars and stakeholders. The data sets are made available, unless otherwise stated, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a license with equivalent rights, following the principle ‘as open as possible as closed as necessary’. As per the Grant Agreement, metadata of deposited data will be open and available under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent.

In general, data are made openly available to validate the research results immediately at the time of publication of public reports and scientific papers. Data are given full citation from official project publications and websites and they are made available through institutional or public data repositories compliant with OpenAIRE requirements (See Tab. 2).

The research data that are made openly available are deposited in open formats in repositories that guarantee long term preservation and will be re-usable by third parties after the end of the project.

Back-up copies of the research data that cannot be shared and cannot be deposited in institutional or public data repositories will be safely stored for at least 5 years after the project ends.

The quality of the data will be carefully assured by scrupulously adhering to FAIR data principles and standard best practices in the handling of qualitative data.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to data and publications, in the frame of PANICOENE we will produce:

- 1) a series of events with scholars, practitioners and stakeholders: academics, journalists, activists, artists, migration and border specialists, climate change specialists, critical theorists, NGO representatives. Events will be archived on the project's website and some of the participants will be commissioned to produce an article or visual contribution for the project's website;
- 2) a podcast on climate change-induced mobilities.

4. Allocation of resources

Making data FAIR requires an investment of money and researchers' time. PANICOENE is not an exception.

During the project, UniBo's institutional cloud storage solution (Microsoft OneDrive) will be adopted to share data among team members. The budget is available to cover the cost of 3 external HD storage devices. A dedicated budget will cover also the costs related to the project website setting up.

For the cost of the data analysis, I will include the cost of Nvivo and Transcribe.

Responsibility for data management usually sits with each dataset creator (generally the team leader but see Table 4 below). Table 5 identifies all contributors participating in data management activities and specifies their roles.

Table 4 – Summary and contacts of people responsible for data management

Name	ORCID (if available)	E-mail address
Elena Giacomelli	0000-0003-1542-5047	elena.giacomelli4@unibo.it

Table 5 – Summary of team members involved in the datasets collection and management.

Name	ORCID (if available)	Role
Elena Giacomelli	0000-0003-1542-5047	PI, Data Collector and Producer

See Annex I for details about data management responsibilities related to each dataset.

5. Data security

During active data management (e.g., during data collection and analysis), research data stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard-drives are accessible only after

logging in with username and password (periodically modified according to national law provisions for data security) and are protected by updated antiviruses. They are also regularly backed-up in order to avoid accidental losses. None of the project data will ever be left inadvertently available. If external devices are used to store data files (e.g., backup files), they will be kept in a safe place accessible only to the researchers involved or will be encrypted with ad-hoc software.

The cloud storage solution (One Drive) will be adopted for data sharing among team members. In this case, too, regular backup of the data will be performed to ensure data recovery.

Long-term preservation of public data is ensured by the chosen data repositories that have specific preservation policies.

6. Ethical or legal aspects

Ethical aspects related to data sharing and protection are discussed at length as part of a comprehensive ethics approach developed by the project team in consultation with an ethics advisor. The project has been submitted to the University of Bologna's Bioethics Committee. Both information sheets on the research and privacy form with information on the processing of personal data and on pursuant to art. 13 of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 have been created and are going to be distributed to participants of the research. The participants will have to return them signed.

Annex I: Datasets

The analytic description of each expected dataset of the PANICOENE project is included in this Annex.

Datas et numb er	Ready at month of project	<i>Dataset title</i>
1	36	<i>Semi-structured Interviews</i>
Status		<i>Not yet available</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Version		Not yet available
Creator/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOENE
Contributor/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOENE
Contact Person/s		Giacomelli Elena (PI)
Contents		Semi-structured interviews on climate change-induced mobilities and on collaboration between targets of the project with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Academics; - Journalists; - Activists and Artivists
Data format		ODT (for text), MP3 (for audio), MP4 (for video)
Data volume		10MB to 100GB, depending on the number of audio/video interviews
Accessibility		When possible, anonymised versions of the interviews will be openly available.
Related publication/s		Not yet available

Datas et numb er	Ready at month of project	<i>Dataset title</i>
1	42	<i>Qualitative materials generated in the context of workshops and focus groups</i>
Status		<i>Not yet available</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Version		Not yet available
Creator/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOENE
Contributor/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOENE
Contact Person/s		Giacomelli Elena (PI)
Contents		Materials that are produced in the context of workshops carried out with academics; researchers; journalists; activists and artists. The type of

Datas et numb er	Ready at month of project	Dataset title
1	42	<i>Qualitative materials generated in the context of workshops and focus groups</i>
Status		<i>Not yet available</i>
		materials produced (maps, visual artefacts, writing, etc.) and whether or not these might be stored and/or made publicly available will be decided in consultation with workshop participants.
Data format		ODT (for text), MP3 (for audio), MP4 (for video); JPEG (for images)
Data volume		10MB to 100GB, depending on the type and amount of materials
Accessibility		Whether or not the materials produced in the context of these workshops might be stored and/or made publicly available will be decided in consultation with workshop participants. It is imperative for the successful realization of the workshops that participants are entrusted with ample decision-making power on these questions, as the feeling of being coerced into publishing results publicly might lead potential participants to withdraw their participation
Related publication/s		Not yet available

Datas et numb er	Ready at month of project	Dataset title
1	36	<i>Qualitative data from critical discourse analysis of narratives and discourse on CCIM</i>
Status		<i>Not yet available</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Version		Not yet available
Creator/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOCENE
Contributor/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOCENE
Contact Person/s		Giacomelli Elena (PI)
Contents		Analysis of media content through critical discourse analysis
Data format		ODT (for text), MP3 (for audio), MP4 (for video); JPEG (for images)
Data volume		10MB to 100GB, depending on the type and amount of materials
Accessibility		When possible, the content of the analysis will be openly available.
Related publication/s		Not yet available

Dataset number	Ready at month of project	Dataset title
1	42	<i>Platform (free access and registration on a voluntary base): identification data, role, gender, contact data.</i>
Status		<i>Not yet available</i>
ID [ID type]		Not yet available
Version		Not yet available
Creator/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOCENE
Contributor/s		Giacomelli Elena PANICOCENE
Contact Person/s		Giacomelli Elena (PI)
Contents		Data for the creation of a platform of collaboration
Data format		ODT (for text), MP3 (for audio), MP4 (for video); JPEG (for images)
Data volume		10MB to 100GB, depending on the type and amount of materials
Accessibility		When possible, the content will be openly available.
Related publication/s		Not yet available